

LANGUAGE CHARACTERISTICS OF EXTREMIST TEXT

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Abstract: In accordance with the new version of the law "On countering extremist activity", a criminal offense is not only the publication (replication, popularization) of extremist works, but also the creation of texts of extremist content. If earlier investigative practice encountered only the figure of the Distributor, then from now on, a completely new figure, the Author, should enter the field of professional vision of operatives. Apparently, this innovation will cause certain difficulties in investigative and judicial practice: distribution is a concrete, physical act, while the creation of a text is a creative process that is not fixed by the usual methods of forensic science.

Key words: extremism, writing, author's tests.

Cultural affiliation is a person's belonging to a certain social, professional community (environment of workers or intellectuals, doctors or economists, etc.). Cultural affiliation reveals itself in a specific worldview and language. So, a doctor can give out a somewhat cool attitude to the physical suffering of a person, his death; but when discussing unemployment or low wages, the doctor may get emotional. The economist, on the other hand, will experience sacred awe before the category of human death; but will look at unemployment without aggression - as an economic phenomenon, natural in the current conditions. The professional and social affiliation of a person is given out by a terminological apparatus that breaks into speech even in situations not related to professional activities.

Categories that are especially relevant for the author's study of extremist materials. The subject of extremist thought is society, its structure and functioning. The subjects of extremist activity set themselves global tasks to change the social structure, the state system. The fulfillment of these tasks will be obviously impossible if an extremist thinker confines himself to discussions in elite circles of like-minded people and opponents. Only with a massive impact on the broad masses do extremist goals have a chance of being realized. From this, an important property of the current under study is derived - the desire for a powerful performing apparatus, an indispensable collectivity. As a consequence, we can talk about a potential discrepancy between the identity of the distributor and the creator of an extremist work.

Before the amendments to the Federal Law “On Counteracting Extremist Activity” came into force, it was enough for operatives to record the act of disseminating the material and find the actual distributor. From now on, not only the distribution of extremist literature, but also its creation is a criminal offense. This means that when fixing the fact of distribution of material, investigators should solve an additional task: to find out whether the distributor is also the author of the work. With a positive answer, the fault of the distributor is aggravated, with a negative answer, the investigation has a new perspective: the search for the author.

Thus, the first important task of the author's research on extremist materials is to answer the question of whether a particular distributor can be the creator of the work he is distributing at the same time. In the event that extremist materials contain open attribution (declared affiliation) of some well-known, large organization, i.e. it makes sense to assume that there is a division of responsibilities between the creator of a work and the distributor.

The author of the work, most likely, is the leading subject, the ideologist of the organization, the generator of ideas; the distributor is a slave subject, a physical executor. As a rule, distributors who are members of large extremist organizations are strongly influenced by the leaders of the movement, who create ideological works. The guided subject, as a rule, is not capable of creating an original speech work that has sufficient attractiveness and persuasiveness.

In this case, the tactics of expert proof of the identity / non-identity of the author of the work and its distributor will be reduced to establishing the creative ability (inability) of the distributor to create the text he distributes. The indicated creative ability is made up of such characteristics as cultural level, language competence, socio-cultural affiliation, as well as personal originality. Consequently, the author's study is intended to characterize the author not as a human individual (belonging to a certain gender, speaking a certain dialect), but as a person who is at a certain stage of his socio-cultural development. This is an essential feature of the author's expertise in the context of an investigation into manifestations of extremism.

The cultural level is manifested in the erudition demonstrated by the author of the text. To prove his idea, the creator of a work can cite various historical events, establish parallels between the characters of the work and famous personalities (public figures, politicians, writers, etc.). The author will be characterized by the depth of the problem he poses; the ability to see contradictions in the surrounding world, to identify

their causes, to establish relationships. The linguistic competence of a person consists of the breadth of his vocabulary, the ability to use proverbs (folk proverbs and sayings), the ability to introduce phraseology into his speech. A striking characteristic of a person's linguistic "freedom" is the ability to operate with syntactic constructions of various types and degrees of complexity.

So, the speaker can confine himself in his speech to simple sentences with a direct word order or express his thought in more complex syntactic forms (combine two (three, four) sentences into one, building between the parts subordinate relations of a certain logical type (consequence, cause, time, places, etc.)). An indicative factor will be the breadth of use of book clichés in speech, as well as book punctuation marks (ellipsis, colon, semicolon). The category of personal originality characterizes a person by the fact of his presence. Each of us in our thinking, behavior and speech implements a lot of stereotypes. Education, the acquisition of life experience lies precisely in the accumulation of stereotypical knowledge and skills accumulated by society.

However, from a certain period of life, a person begins to develop an individual style: original thinking, an individual system of values, author's speech techniques.

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The professional and social affiliation of a person is given out by a terminological apparatus that breaks into speech even in situations not related to professional activities. A specialist-authorologist is able to characterize the author of the studied work in a qualified manner according to the described personal parameters. A similar conclusion can be drawn from the results of observations of the speech and behavior of the detained distributor. Comparative research will answer the question of whether the distributor is able to create a distributed text. An author's study of the type described will help to justify (or accuse) the distributor on an additional point of authorship.

However, any investigator will reasonably have the question of whether it is possible to base conclusions about authorship on indicators of the cultural level, how

fully it is possible to simulate the considered personal characteristics of linguistic competence and sociocultural affiliation. This issue needs to be considered. It is really possible to imitate a professional or social affiliation, although it is not easy. The imitator needs to become familiar with professional terminology or social jargon, but this is not enough. It is necessary to learn a special style of speech characteristic of a sociocultural group: a system of assessments, logical stereotypes when constructing a text, and finally, a typical syntax. The latter characteristics are difficult to imitate, but theoretically forgery is possible.

Signs of cultural level and linguistic competence are imitated only relatively: only downwards. This means that a person with high levels of cultural level and language competence may well imitate the speech of a person with low levels of these same parameters. But the reverse situation is impossible. Therefore, if texts of a socio-political content, moreover, talentedly written, are seized from a person, young and poorly educated, then the authorship of the detained young man is obviously unlikely.

Thus, in the investigation of criminal manifestations of extremism, the use of methods of judicial autonomy is associated with certain specifics dictated by the type of crime. The new version of the Federal Law "On Counteracting Extremist Activity" will most likely contribute to the fact that forensic linguistic expertise will move from the category of non-standard, one-time investigative moves to the category of mandatory forensic activities to investigate verbal forms of manifestation of extremism.

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